

USING SYSTEMATIC-ACTIVITY APPROACH IN TEACHING VISUAL PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Algorithm and programming in general secondary schools is one of the basic departments of "Informatics and information technologies". Because by studying the department of algorithmization and programming, it is possible to form students' critical, logical and algorithmic thinking in the field of informatics and information technologies, to create an idea about the possibilities of programming [1, 2]. But due to the appearance of various computer applications and the development of social networks, the expansion of the possibilities of the global network, students' interest in algorithmic and programming problems is waning. Therefore, today, the development of approaches aimed at increasing students' interest in programming, especially in the visual programming language, remains one of the urgent issues facing general secondary schools [3-6]. Today, general secondary schools teach the use of visual (Scratch), programming languages and use them to program examples and problems. It is considered appropriate to use a systematic-activity approach to increase the effectiveness of teaching this visual programming language [2].

Therefore, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms of using the systematic-activity approach in increasing the effectiveness of teaching Scratch programming languages and in forming students' logical thinking about programming. To do this, it is necessary to first define the goals and objectives of using a systematic-activity approach in teaching programming languages:

- Formation of students' critical thinking style in the process of teaching Scratch visual programming languages;
- Development of students' skills of independent work with educational material and information using the method of mental maps related to the Scratch visual programming language;
- formation of students' skills to find, process, transfer and receive the necessary information related to the Scratch programming language, to use different strategies in its processing, to reject unnecessary or incorrect information;
- To increase the quality and efficiency of the educational process by implementing the opportunities of educational technologies to increase the effectiveness of teaching Scratch visual programming languages;
- formation of students' skills in creating practical projects in the process of mastering new knowledge of Scratch visual programming languages.

Based on such tasks, the following are provided:

- formation of students' readiness for self-development and continuous education related to Scratch visual programming;
- formation of pupils' competence in programming problems using the Scratch visual programming language;
- formation of students' cognitive activity related to algorithmization and programming.

Thus, increasing the effectiveness of teaching the Scratch visual programming language in secondary schools involves activating the students' cognitive activity, mastering computer literacy, acquiring new knowledge in the educational process, and updating their mental activity related to information technologies by using the systematic-activity approach.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop improved mechanisms of using the systematic-activity approach to increase the effectiveness of teaching Scratch visual programming language in general secondary schools and to increase students' logical algorithmic thinking about programming and to form their competencies.

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